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Challenges of Ready-Made Garments Sector in Bangladesh: Ways to Overcome

Md. Abdur Rakib¹ and ATM Adnan²

Abstract

The ready-made garments (RMG) sector has a greater potential than any other sector in terms of employment and foreign exchange earnings to reduce poverty and make a contribution to the national economy. Along with its potentiality the sector is also experiencing new challenges which can be the future determinants of its sustainability. The present study has made on descriptive research, is conducted to identify different dimension of challenges in readymade garment industry in Bangladesh and a feasible solution to cope up the challenges. To accomplish result research technique has relied based on information from secondary sources. From the inception of RMG in 1978 Bangladesh has seen a tremendous growth of the number of factories in consistent with the amount of export. In year 1983-84 there were only 134 RMG units where only 40000 workers were working in this sector but in 2013-2014 the number of RMG units increases around 6000 with the employment of around 4.2 million workers among them almost 80% are female. This sector also faces a lot of challenges like unskilled workers, improper infrastructure, electricity crisis, gas shortage, insufficient bank loan associated with high rate of interest, high tax rate, intricate social compliance, political crisis, market and product diversification, lack of new investment, poor backward and forward linkage etc. In order to overcome these challenges, we need to take number collaborative and coordinated steps to be taken from both owners and major stakeholders to reach the ultimate goal of achieving the top position in the world apparel market.

KeyWords: RMG Sector, Challenges, BGMEA, Ways to Overcome

1. Introduction

Bangladesh is an emerging economy in the world, a small country in Southeast Asia with high population density. The readymade garments industry of Bangladesh commonly known as the RMG sector is the top ambassador of Bangladesh as a country in the global market. Bangladesh positioned itself in number right after china in terms of total apparel production and export. RMG export earning undoubtedly holds the significant position in the countries total export after the 90s (Faruque, 2014) and one of the major contributor in GDP of Bangladesh. It seems like that the export performance of RMG can easily be argued as the total Export performance of Bangladesh and strength of the economy. The journey of the RMG industry started in the late 70's and since then it has played a key player role in the economy (Haider, 2007). Within a very short period of time it has become the largest export earner of the country through a major positive forward thrust in the early 90s (Shahriar et al., 2014). This industry has not just contributed through the dollar earning but also in socioeconomic prospects, creating a huge number employment opportunities mostly for the poor illiterate workforce of the country. Through the export of Apparels products Bangladesh now become a flagship brand in the developed countries of the globe where the products have been exported such as, European Union countries (59% of total Export), USA (29%) and other parts of the world (15%) (BGMEA, 2015). The hold of RMG in the total export earning has reached more than 81% in fiscal year of 2013-2014 and it shares almost 16% of total GDP and also the trend of RMG contribution are strongly predicted to be increased in the upcoming year (Mahmud, 2012). In FY 2013-2014 RMG industry providing direct earning opportunities to more than 4 million labor force and earns 22 billion US\$ form exporting the apparels. The growth of factories in RMG industry has a key indicator how this industry has grown so fast with a number of 134 factories in FY1983-84 to

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4222 in FY 2013-14 (BGMEA, 2015). RMG sector has played a Nobel role in empowering women by providing them employment. But these particulars workforces potentiality cannot be used fully because of the illiteracy (Paul- Majumder, 1998). Garments industry has achieved a lot since its inception but there is no omega point for achievement still there are lots of things to do, lots of peak to climb (Wayss, 2015). New prospects and new challenges are to be addressed. After the major life taking accident of Rana Plaza and Tazrin garments, workplace safety has become the most talking challenge of RMG. Apart from the government initiative global brands and retailers have taken major private initiatives through creation of the Bangladesh Accord on Fire and Building Safety 'Accord' and the Alliance for Bangladesh Worker Safety 'Alliance'. Both the Accord and the Alliance are consisting mainly of multinational corporations from North America and Europe to ensure the workplace and labor safety of the RMG units all over the Bangladesh (Labowitz & Pauly, 2014). Most of the garment factories in Bangladesh are not the voluntary followers of the labour law and ILO conventions (Islam & Ahmed, 2010). After passing the post MFA period quite successfully with a high growth of both the dollar and quantity export still Bangladeshi RMG industry is facing challenges in product diversifying, new market entry and positioning, weak infrastructure, inefficient backward linkage and almost no forward integration or brand development and promotion (Robbani, 2000). High dependencies on exported raw material especially in case of woven garments are major reason for high lead time. The component of backward industries linkage includes weaving the fabric, spinning the yarn, and dyeing, printing and finishing operation (Siddiqi, 2005). Bangladeshi RMG industry is established through providing low value apparels products with low price. There are very less interest in developing technical knowledge, training and innovation, research and development. That ultimately reduces the competitiveness in the long run. In association with that low motivation, monotony for repetitive work, rapid technological change and high cost that reduced innovation can be major challenges to be dealt with in near future (Abdullah, 2005). Challenges could be the Political violence at the national level often influences unrest at the RMG sector (Uddin & Jahed 2007). Efficiency has been always the problem for sea ports of Bangladesh. Low efficiency directly results in the increase of cost. (World bank, 1999) reveals that one average size container handling charge is consecutively almost three times and two times more in Bangladesh in comparison to Thailand and Colombo. That ultimately resulted in loss to economy by \$ 600 Million per annum. Bangladesh is known for cheap labor and leap lower case low value garments which is higher in quantity but lower in value. So challenge is to strive for high value products and consecutively search for new market destinations. Moreover, natural disaster or Act of Gods are unavoidable but affect garment industry. Garment order of (US\$ 15,000 million) could not be exported on time due to the flood of 1998. More than 3 lakh workers were victim of the flood (Quddus & Rashid 1999). World political and economic situation is a major challenge for Bangladeshi RMG sector. Still, the most basic questions about Challenges of RMG in Bangladesh and threat to development is how the government, factory owners, BGMEA, International associations and buyers jointly work to find effective routes to overcome the challenges.

Although many significant studies have been done to identify the prospect and challenges of the RMG industry, these studies did not resulted with uniform findings and no particular academic endeavor have not been run to accumulate all the crucial findings regarding the prospects and challenges of the RMG industry. This review study tries to gather all the findings allied to the challenges of RMG sector in Bangladesh and tries to seek out possible approaches to overcome the challenges of RMG in Bangladesh

2. Literature Review

Literature review shows the overall scenario of the RMG sector, its contribution to the Economy and challenges associated with the growth of this sector. In spite of its major contribution in export earning, the sector is facing lots of challenges towards achieving its full potentiality. Islam (2015) conducts that RMG sector singularly assures employment of almost 4.4 million workers among them 80% are women therefore empowering women. It holds the highest portion of share in export earning with approximately

\$23 billion of export which is 81% of the total export. Despite of being a major driver of Economy RMG sectors are facing challenges regarding ensuring workers safety and welfare, poor infrastructure, lack of training and research, low productivity, lack of skilled workforce and immense competition from the rival country.

Mahmud (2012) investigates RMG industry helps to increase the GDP by 4.39 %. In fiscal year 2011-2012 RMG exports raised at a figure of USD 19.91 billion and around 81% of state export earnings, that was about 4%-5% total exports around the world. Hasan (2013) examines that since 2005, the challenge becomes the unbound opportunities. The industry has immersed with its full potential with low cost apparels and low cost labor. But the industry is also facing some new challenges as the industry is going towards its full potentiality such as poor infrastructure, lack of backward linkages, high lead time and market and product diversification. Despite the epic growth of our RMG industry, and its bright prospects, challenges are still there. One of the biggest challenges currently faced by our RMG industry is to ensure workplace safety and better working conditions for the millions of garment workers.

Clark & Kanter (2011) analyze the efficiency level judge by the productivity of Bangladeshi workers is not up to date or accordance to international level. Empirical study found that it is just one-fourth of that of Chinese workers. Low literacy rate is the main reason for that. Rahman et al. (2008) survey on RMG workers' productivity reveals, the proportion of skilled workers is high in large factories (46-53%) than small and medium factories. The proportion of unskilled workers is high in small and medium enterprises (18-26%) than that of large enterprises (16-18%). Berik & Rodgers (2008) address Bangladeshi RMG owners are very reluctant to invest for any training and development facilities. Although study reveals that training costs are directly offset by the productivity increase.

Berg et al., (2011) find five major challenges on the basis of significance identified by McKinsey & Company, Inc based on survey of Chief Purchasing officers from frontline apparels companies in Europe and USA sourcing from Bangladesh. These are weak infrastructures, Compliance issues, low supplier and labor efficiency, Insufficient backward linkage and last but not the least political and economic volatility. Chowdhury et al. (2014) analyze on different management level of Bangladeshi garments factory identifying majority portion of the managers pointed out utility crisis such as oil and gas shortage, too much dependency on imported raw material, suppliers' inefficiency and low labor productivity, high interest rate and insufficient bank finance and also the political unrest as major challenges for RMG. Need for product and market diversification, positive branding, safety management, strong lobbying and diplomacy for favorable trade policy with lucrative market representative, effective negotiation skills development and unfavorable tax policies are some other important challenges associated with the RMG of Bangladesh ("Report casts shadow,"2014). Schwab (2014) address the infrastructure facilities consisting of road network, sea and land port facilities and last but not the least utility such as electricity and gas supply are the top most challenges for Bangladeshi RMG Sector. Construction of new and up gradation of existing Road-Rail-Port facilities are now become major requirements for RMG growth and sustainability. Bangladesh as a developing nation is positioned 109 among 144 countries of the world and stands behind India and Sri Lanka on the basis of infrastructure quality. Rahman and Anwar (2007) find weak and inadequate infrastructures such as poor energy supply, poor port facilities are the common challenges facing by the RMG sector in Bangladesh. Another problem is port congestion. RMG sector often faces huge losses due to the inefficiency of Bangladesh port. To remain competitive in the world market one of the important strategies is product and market diversification. Chowdhury et al. (2005) examine Bangladesh is further challenged because most of the labours are unskilled with low productivity which results in increased per unit cost of production. For example- productivity of Bangladeshi workers is one-fourth of that of Chinese. Moreover, natural calamity often affected garment industry. Islam et al. (2014) identify this sector is struggling with a number of problems. Conflict between owners and workers, labor unrest, shortage of gas and electricity, poor infrastructure, poor port facility, lead time complexities,

conspiracy of home and abroad, advancing competitors in the quota free international market are some of them which are posing a great threat to its survival. Nathan (2013) finds that after the Rana Plaza disaster, a number of global buyers have come forward to put up some money to improve factory safety conditions. Different schemes have been proposed by a group of largely European buyers, called the Alliance (2013), along with the ILO, and another group of US buyers, called the Accord (2013). The Alliance is based on a binding commitment, which can be subject to arbitration. The Accord is signed by European companies and international unions, with an ILO official to oversee the process. Hassan (2014) argues the significant challenges of RMG behind the shadow of its successes are the workplace safety and better working condition for almost 4 million workers. Sarwar (2013) attempt to identify poor infrastructure such as gas and electricity crisis bound factory owners to use backup generators and alternative power sources which results in increase in the cost of production. Ahmed (2014) find corruption and bureaucratic inefficiencies are also addressed as major challenges for industrial growth. The economic and political stability, availability of trained and efficient workforce, strong supply chain management, weak backward linkage are becoming major concern for the RMG sector.

3. Methodology

The study has made on descriptive research, is conducted to identify different dimension of challenges in readymade garment industry in Bangladesh. To come up with the result, researchers were not required to visit the factory. For this reason, researchers have ignored the direct data collection and surveys. Consequently the research technique has relied based on information from secondary sources. Those data collected through Journals, Research articles, Thesis papers, newspapers case studies, online news paper and survey reports, garments Manufacturing Industries Annual reports, BGMEA Yearly report and Files. The data was collected basically through skimming and scanning out the findings of different secondary source. After the completion of the data collection descriptive analyses was used illustrate the data. At the first phases, analysis has been done to identify the challenges of RMG of Bangladesh and the second phase illustrates the measures to cope up with the challenges to move towards the top position in the world apparel market. This study did not use any unethical means to collect information.

4. Study Findings

Since 2005 the RMG of Bangladesh has become the top export earner of Bangladesh and positioned itself in the frontline of the world apparel market. But every success comes along with the new challenges. Challenges like poor infrastructures, high lead time, weak backward industry and inefficient supply chain management and more over low safety measures make the success of RMG somehow vulnerable these days (Hasan, 2013). We are to address these challenges in the following parts of the paper.

4.1 Unskilled workers

For the development of an industry, it is necessary to have sufficient skilled with required expertise. As the Bangladeshi garments industry is in the open market competition after Quota system has been removed in 2005 the RMG industry of Bangladesh is largely need to upgrade skill of respective operatives and executives. The insufficient size of the skilled workforce, particularly in middle management, is hampering growth in this industry. The industry is currently employing 4.2 million workers, where about 80% is women and they are mostly illiterate, unskilled and came from the rural and report part of the country. Lower level of expertise hamper our productivity, which is 77%. This is lower than our main competitors (India 92%, Vietnam 90% and Pakistan 88%). Though over the year a good backward linkage has developed, we still fall short in forward linkage (Islam, 2015). Most of the factories do not have in house training facilities and the existing training facilities are ranked as poor in quality due to lack of professional qualified trainers, weak training program (irregular courses and covered only workers), lack of teaching/training aids, no systematic training needs assessment or evaluation program, no follow up and feedback intervention, no corollary relation between training and benefits in terms of cash or kind, etc. (Khan, 2010). (Rahman et al., 2008) found that the average skill level of almost fifty percent sampled

surveyed first line operators is ranges from zero to minimal and the primary reason identified was lack of technical training apart from on job training.

4.2 Improper Infrastructure:

Inadequate and improperly built infrastructure may hamper investment. This is a serious issue for Bangladesh. Twenty-one percent of businesses, surveyed in Bangladesh as part of the Global Competitiveness Report 2014–2015, pointed out that insufficient supply of infrastructure as the top barrier to doing business in Bangladesh.

Factory premises Infrastructure: at the point of inception of the RMG industry, garments factories were mostly set up in an unplanned manner mostly in converted and shared building, there was no purpose built building on that time (Islam, 2013). The consequences of those unplanned issues are showing off now though the happening of destructive disaster like Rana plaza and Tazrin garments which killed almost 2000 people and injured another thousand (Azim, 2013). These issues become serious now among the EU and USA buyers. They are now more serious in ensuring the building and workplace safety. Accord and Alliance are developed to address and correct the major faults and risks associated with workplace. As the RMG sector hold major portion in Export earning and share a handsome contribution of GDP, infrastructure development is the major challenge in the way of developing safe factories and workplace for workers.

4.3 Transportation Infrastructure:

4.3.1 Road network-

Poor condition of the highways due to the improper construction and maintenance exhibits a major threat to the improvement of lead time of RMG. The Dhaka Chittagong highways serving as a main route of transportation is always busy with huge traffic and often took 12 hours to cover the distance. The narrow two lane high ways and movement of all modes of transportation makes the transportation more delayed (Sattar, 2015).

4.3.2 Railway system-

Despite having too much potentiality in a sense of freight and uninterrupted transportation, the rail roads are not utilized properly. The rail container storage facilities in Chittagong and Dhaka are not sufficient therefore reducing the interest of the exporters and importers. The inefficient wagon management and improper yard layout also can be added with the problems.

4.3.3 Sea ports-

The Chittagong port, which handles nearly 85 percent of the country's trade merchandise, suffers from labor problems, poor management, and lack of equipment (World Bank, 1999). These bureaucratic red tape inefficiencies and corruption tremendously affect the competitiveness of Bangladeshi garment in the world market (Robbani, 2000). Transportation problem also arise due to the national and local level political agendas (Mansur, 2013). Productivity and efficiency of Chittagong port is not competitive in comparison to other south Asian port such as Colombo and Mumbai. Chittagong port suffers from high Lead time as well for sea freight is increased by about ten days due to the lack of a deep-sea harbor needed for entry of the mother vessel. (Berg et al., 2011).

4.4 Energy crisis: Electricity crisis, Gas shortage etc.

Lucrative Open market policy of investment in Bangladeshi Garments sector is almost unsuccessful due to the power crisis and utility facilities. Such as Gas, oil, Electricity, Water which are the basic prerequisite of industry development. The load-shedding of electricity cause a rapid decrease in production which also reduced the export order. The cost of production has risen due to instant increase in electricity tariff. These frequent electricity disruptions force factory owners to use alternative source of energy like generator and IPP (Independent Power Plant) which increase their cost of production further. A Spokesman for the

Bangladesh Textile Mills Corporation (BTMC) has argued that 60 to 70 per cent of the factory had been affected due to extreme Gas and Electricity shortage and was unable to accept export orders coming in from around the globe (Mazedul, 2013). Power shortfall resulted in loss of production worth of USD 1.6 million per day due to electricity crisis (Zadeed, 2013).

4.5 Bank Loan and High Rate of Interest

The continuity of tight monetary policy causes an intensive increase in cost of production. Due to high interest rate financing cost increases which cause a severe effect on production. The withholding tax of 1% also effects the production badly. The high cost of doing business is because of intensive increase in the rate of interest which has increased the problems of the industry. Bangladeshi RMG exporters had been facing severe competition in the international market due to high service charge and interest on bank loan. There is clearly seen form the lending rate comparison that except of Myanmar the interest rate is highest among all the major RMG exporting countries.

Table-1: Lending interest rate%

Country	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Bangladesh	13.0	13.3	13.0	13.0	13.0
China	5.8	6.6	6.0	6.0	5.6
India	8.3	10.2	10.6	10.3	10.3
Japan	1.6	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.2
Myanmar	17.0	16.3	13.0	13.0	13.0
Pakistan	14.0	14.4	13.5	12.0	11.7

Source: The World Bank, 2015

4.6 Tax rate

As the tenure for the special tax rate for readymade garment and knitwear exporters expired on June 30, 2014. RMG exporters may see a large hike in the tax on their export earnings from the upcoming fiscal year 2015-16. It is seen as a major challenge for RMG exporter. Since 2005 until June 30, 2014, RMG sector has been facilitated by the government through an estimated tax rate of 10% at the time of annual tax assessment as part of measures for helping the main export industry is to strengthen their position in the global market. RMG exporters also may find themselves paying more tax rate from the nest fiscal year 2015-16 (Mala, 2015).

4.7 Social Compliance

Social compliance in Bangladesh ready-made garments industry has been a fundamental requirement for many of the western buyers and it is also considered as the main challenge after the disastrous accidents happened in Tajrin garments and Rana Plaza. The social compliance in Bangladesh garments industry has been talked vastly as different NGOs, media and other foreign buyers are closely monitoring the labor working environment and safety standards. However, Bangladesh Labor Act reformed in July 15, 2013, shows conformity with ILO. Therefore, the labor act in Bangladesh fulfills most of the fundamental rules and regulations that encourage the development of working safety and working environment. The implementation of labor law in every factory is becoming a new challenge.

4.8 Political crisis

According to European and US CPO report, economy and political stability are the fifth in Bangladesh CPOs stated that they will reduce the sourcing from Bangladesh if the political stability were to decrease. Planning security, political unrest, strike and corruption are the main obstacles to hamper economic growth. Political instability is one the main reasons that has made the garments industry suffer along with some of the other industries in Bangladesh. According to Asian Studies Center, Bangladesh is one of the most

politically vulnerable countries both in the world and in Asia. The country ranked sixth in Asia and 29th in the world with 92.5 points. The political unrest, complicated policies, backed by corrupted administration is badly damaging the productivity and goodwill of the RMG industry (Hossain et al., 2011).

4.9 Market and Product Diversification

Bangladeshi RMG products are mainly destined to the US and EU., Within the tenure of last 3 decades Bangladesh has moved up and established itself from a mediocre position to consecutively 2nd and 3rd place in EU and USA. As currently more than 80 per cent of apparel export sourced to USA and EU. The EU market flourishes because of the Quota System and low price product range of Bangladesh. But empirical analysis reveals that the result could have been much better if the duty free access in EU was utilized wisely and efficiently IN EU countries, Germany, UK, France, Italy are the major sourcing country holding almost 80% of the total export in EU. Dependency on only few big buyers are vulnerable, rather Bangladesh should search for new market in the EU for reducing the dependency from big buyers. No traditional Market such as that Japan, Australia, South Korea, Brazil, Mexico, Hong Kong, Taiwan, China, Singapore, Russia and United Arab Emirates could be new potential destinations for Bangladesh's apparel products with quality, low production costs matching with the taste of consumers of developed nations (Rahman, 2015). Bangladesh RMG export are mainly concentrated on T Shirt, Shirt, Sweater and jeans, these are low value added products with low marginal profits and holds almost 75% of Bangladeshi RMG products. Economy of scale is must for this product for profit retention. In the globalized economy and ever-changing fashion world, product diversification is the key to continuous business success. Starting with a few items, the entrepreneurs of the RMG sector have to diversify the product base ranging from ordinary shirts, T-shirts, trousers, shorts, pajamas, ladies and children's wear to sophisticated high value items.

4.10 Lack of new investment:

Bangladesh is facing problems in attracting the new investment both international and Locally in RMG Sector (Bangladesh Observer-Business Survey, 2009). Pessimistic attitude from the local entrepreneurs are opposing the international firms to enter in the local RMG sector specially the lower level product market (Moazzem, 2012). They would only allow the International firms to settle in particular are where the local firms have no expertise. Apparel exporters, both woven and knitwear have demanded a ban on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in ready-made garment (RMG) sector outside the Export Processing Zones (EPZs) as the government withdrew the ban in 2006 to woo FDI in RMG sector. The main Fear of Local Investor in joint venture with the international firm is the labour unrest over the wage issue. There is also a competitiveness issue that international firms can use their reputation and expertise to make the local firms to kick out from the competition (Ziaur, 2012). It has been the demand from the local investors that international firm should only be allowed to invest to develop backward linkage and high value products.

4.11 Coverage of accord and alliance

The Accord and Alliance are now become one of the major challenge for Bangladeshi apparel industry ((Islam, 2015). The Accord and alliance are two different independent organization empowered by apparel brands, retailers and importers both from Europe and USA. The objective of accord and alliance is to work towards a safe and healthy Bangladeshi Ready-Made Garment Industry Bangladesh's major RMG markets are in Europe almost 60% followed by almost 30% in USA. So meet the guidelines and safety instructions regarding the fire and building safety of accord and alliance is a major challenge to achieve competitiveness for international competition for the local investors and importers. Sometimes the condition imposed by the Accord and Alliance requires combined efforts and huge financial investment such as Infrastructural remodelling, factory shifting and relocating and high investment in fire safety equipments.

4.12 Raw materials

The post-MFA trade environment has created a dual challenge to Bangladesh: firstly, Bangladesh has needed to access raw materials at a competitive price and also RMG sector is now competing with hitherto restricted countries in a quota-free environment (Bhattacharya & Rahman, 2001). Bangladesh's dependency on imports creates sourcing risks and longer lead times. Whereas the average fabric lead time for woven in Bangladesh is seven days, it increased to up to 15 days when sourced from India and up to 30 days when sourced from China (McKinsey, 2011). Besides prices of cotton and other raw material used in textile industry fluctuate rapidly in Bangladesh.

4.13 Lack of Research and Development (R & D)

In the absence of a world class research and design institute, Bangladesh's RMG factories make clothing items in accordance with the designs supplied from buyers' end, which is popularly known as 'cut and paste development'. Therefore Bangladesh is still concentrating on low value products. With proper research on branding and fashion trend Bangladesh can capture the high value end products segments. The Research center of both BGMEA and BKMEA conducting post export research that means crunching the export numbers. According to international buyers at present, the RMG sector suffers from 25 percent shortage of skilled workers (Mirdha, 2009). Negotiation skill of the Bangladeshi merchandiser is also poor due to the lack of training. There are only few educational and training institute giving apparel technology related education but the number as well the quality is not up to the mark. However very few initiatives are taken for new products development from these institutes.

5. Recommendation: A way to overcome the problems

The goal of Bangladeshi RMG is to achieve 50 Billion export targets by year 2021 which will cover the 8% of total apparel export of the world market. Currently the country holds approximately 5% of that with 24 billion dollar export. To conquer that target along with the parallel target of emerging a middle income country of government, necessary cohesive actions should be taken.

5.1 Infrastructure

To create a sustainable industry, strong infrastructure is must. Government should play a major role in creating better infrastructure through proper investment in the roads, highways and port facilities. Dhaka-Chittagong four lane highways should be given top most importance; along with the Chittagong port Mongla port should be utilized at their full capacity. The rail road facility between Dhaka and Chittagong need to be improved through proper yard layout, storage facility and wagon management. National Air Carrier (Biman) should extend their cargo wing through giving priority for RMG export at reasonable freight. Deep sea ports and specialized industrial zone for RMG should be given pace.

5.2 Increased Productivity through Research and Training

Only cheap labor will not be the competitive advantage in future. Along with cheap labor efficiency and productivity need to be increased. BGMEA along with the government and other international organizations need to take the initiatives of developing skills and expertise of workers, through investment in education and training (Hassan, 2014). A dedicated research institute should be established related to the RMG sector to conduct necessary research on contemporary fashions to cope up with the new technology and trend. Mid level management training also necessary to eradicate the communication gap and to ensure the flow of directions from top management to lower level (Khan, 2014).

5.3 Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

RMG industries need foreign direct investment or investment in form of joint venture, strategic alliance from technologically advanced companies for the product diversification for high value and non-traditional products (Islam, 2015). In order to attract foreign investors, the government of Bangladesh has to give

exclusive incentives, such as no ceiling on investment, flexible revenue transfer policy, tax holidays, tax exemption and duty free importation, income tax exemption up to 3 to 5 years for foreign investor (Razib, 2015).

5.4 Power and Energy

Consistent supply of energy is pre-requisition of the sustainable and lucrative industry; government has to ensure sufficient energy supply (Islam, 2015). Apart from establishing new plant government can encourage green energy or solar panels in a subsidized rate. Encouragement should be given for establishing industry based private commercial power plants.

Subsidized rent base power plant need to be discourages.

5.5 Safety and welfare of workers

Workplace safety has attracted much importance for the sustainable industry (Islam, 2015). To create positive stimulation and high workers involvement up gradation in labor law to implementing effective labor inspection system, regular safety follow up of all garment factories, placement of injured workers, ensuring occupational safety and health, introducing group insurance facility are necessary (Reddy, 2014). The Accord and Alliance guideline of workers and workplace safety should be followed accordingly (Wayss, 2014).

5.6 Political Stability

Over the years, RMG industry has suffered a lot due to the political instability. Therefore political crisis has imposed a major challenge to RMG sector. All political activities need to be kept aside from the business activities. Destructive political actions that increase the lead time or hamper the supply chain such as strike should be banned by government. Mainstream Political involvement other than trade union of factory workers should be controlled.

5.7 Market Diversification and Market Access

Bangladeshi Garments manufacturer and exporter should shift their concentration from the low value end product such as t-shirt to high value product like suits, lingerie for more sustainability of the industry (Hassan, 2014). Potential big markets with large buyer of medium income group such as Russia, Brazil, Spain, Japan, Mexico and India can be a lucrative target for both high and low value ended products. Markets with high annual income and low population can be targeted with high value ended products such as turkey, Austria; Australia Etc. government should play effective diplomatic strategy to ensure market access. Non- tariff barriers such visa problems, embargo on specific product sources, transit problem need to be solved (Islam, 2015).

5.8 Tax Benefit

Bangladeshi RMG sector should enjoy the tax benefit as it is singularly holding 81% of the export earnings. Government should continue the tax benefit of charging fixed 10% rather than 35% tax on apparel export income at least for the next 5 years. Withdrawal of value-added tax waiver up to 100 instead of existing 80 per cent on utility bills can be considered to make the VAT rebate process easier. Source tax rate should be stayed at 0.3% or could be lower rather than 0.6% which has been passed in recent budget (Chowdhury, 2014).

5.9 Buyers Contribution

Buyers of Bangladeshi RMG should not always seek low price but also need to contribute towards the development of the industry and workers. Buyers should help to enhance the supply chain efficiency of the local garments, train local workers and operators with modern technology and process ideas. Vital role

can be played by the buyers in establishing workers and factory safety. They can also play an important role in ensuring labor law and welfare of the labor.

5.10 Need for trade diplomacy

Trade diplomacy of government should be more target and result oriented. Cohesive and consensus measures should be perused by all public and private level business and political groups like ministry of foreign affairs, foreign consulate and embassy of Bangladesh, export promotion bureau, Business and trade association (BGMEA, BKMEA), Export promotion bureau to avail the market access and trade benefits from foreign markets.

6. Conclusion

The readymade garments sector has emerged as a gigantic industry within a short span of time appeared to be crucial to our economy as a source of export earnings and employment generation. The socio-economic scenario of the country is changing as the large workforce is involving themselves in this industry by seeing the steady growth of RMG sector. Adverse effect on this industry come from different points such as weak infrastructure, inefficient port management and utilization, poor negotiation and bargaining capacity, insufficient backup from backward industry and limitation of forward linkage and integration, rapidly increasing competition from international rivals, increasing bargaining power of buyers. These factors adversely restraining the full potentiality of the RMG sector of Bangladesh. By controlling or if possible diminishing these actors and maximize utilization of the competitive advantages such as huge supply of workforce at reasonable pay off can create a further boom in Bangladeshi economy, henceforth can radically change the standard of living and economy in a positive way. To reduce the gap of expectation and reality collaborative and cohesive measures should be taken. Sustainable infrastructure should be developed through creating specialized RMG industry zone, ensuring sufficient power and utility, develop sustainable and lucrative partnership between buyers and sellers through effective political and commercial negotiations, effective and fully implacable technical education facilities should be established to create expertise in this trend and increase efficiency of exiting workforce, low interest loan or special loan instrument should be created for RMG sector, and last but not the least for the sustainability of the RMG industry forward integration through developing positive brand image and accessing new market and product segment is necessary. That would help this industry to boost towards a new level. Putting challenges in one side, a prospering future is awaiting for RMG sector of Bangladesh in near future on the other side. With challenges on one side, a more glittering future is waiting for the ready-made garment industry of Bangladesh.

References

- Abdin, M. J. (2008). Overall Problems and Prospects of Bangladeshi Ready-Made Garment Industry. Retrieved from <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1117186>.
- Abdullah, A.Y.M. (2005). Productivity Development is a Very Crucial Way Out to Face the Post Multi Fiber Agreement Challenges for Bangladesh. *Journal of Business Administratio*, 31(3): 107-129.
- Ahmed, H. U. (2014, October4). RMG sector: Opportunities and challenges, *The Financial Express*, p.2.
- Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA). (2015). *Trade Information*. Retrieved from <http://www.bgmea.com.bd/home/pages/tradeinformation#.VXRqCaZvDI4>
- Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA).(2015). *RMG Export in World wide*. Retrieved from <http://www.bgmea.com.bd/chart-test/rmgExportInWorldwide>

- Berik, G., and Rodgers, Y.V.D.M. (2008). Options for Enforcing Labor Standards: Lessons from Bangladesh and Cambodia. Department of Economics Working Paper Series. Working Paper No: 2008-14. Salt Lake City. Retrieved from <http://www.econ.utah.edu>
- Berg, A., Hedrick, S., Kempf, S. & Tochtermann, T. (2011). *Bangladesh's Ready-made garments landscape: The challenge of growth*. McKinsey & Company, Inc.
- Bhattacharya, D., and Rahman M. (2001). "Bangladesh's Apparel Sector: Growth Trend and the Post-MFA Challenges." In Pratima Paul-Majumder and Binayak Sen (eds.) *Growth of Garment Industry in Bangladesh: Economic and Social Dimensions*. Dhaka: Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies.
- Bhattacharya, D., & Rahman, M. (1999). *Female Employment under Export-Propelled Industrialization: Prospects for Internalizing Global Opportunities in Bangladesh's Apparel Sector*. Paper presented at the UNRISD's Contribution to the Fourth World Conference on Women.
- Chowdhury, M.A.M., Ali, M.M., & Rahman, R. (2005). WTO, Post MFA Era and the Bangladesh RMG Sector: An Assessment of the performance and challenges. *Journal of the Institute of Bankers Bangladesh*, 52 (2):87-120.
- Chowdhury, M., Ahmed, R., & Yasmin, M. (2014). Prospects and Problems of RMG Industry: A study on Bangladesh. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, Vol.5, No.7, 108-109.
- Chowdhury, O. (2014, December 7). RMG Sector: Challenges & Way Forward. *Dhaka Tribune*, Retrieved from <http://www.dhakatribune.com/feature/2014/dec/07/rmg-sector-challenges-way-forward#sthash.f0VleseL.dpuf>
- Clark, C., and Kanter, S. (2011). Violence in the Readymade Garments (RMG) Industry in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 7, No. 3, 1833-8119
- Faruque, H. (2014, September 19). RMG industry of Bangladesh: Past, present and future. *Dhaka Tribune*, Retrieved from <http://www.dhakatribune.com/long-form/2014/sep/19/rmg-industry-bangladesh-past-present-and-future#sthash.72yJndaL.dpuf>
- Haider, M. Z. (2007). Competitiveness of the Bangladesh Ready-made Garment Industry in Major International Markets, *Asia Pacific Trade and Investment Review*, Vol 3 No 1, June, pp. 3-26.
- Hasan, J. (2013). The Competitiveness of Ready Made Garments Industry of Bangladesh in Post MFA Era: How Does the Industry Behave to Face the Competitive Challenge? *British Journal of Economics, Management & Trade*, 3(3): 296-306.
- Hossan, C. G., Sarker, M.A.R., & Afroze, R. (2011). Recent Unrest in the RMG sector of Bangladesh: Is this an outcome of poor labor practices? Retrieved from <http://www.ccsenet.org/journal/index.php/ijbm/article/download/11212/10086>.
- Hossain, T., & Moon, J. (n.d.) (2014). RMG- The Leading Earning Sector in Bangladesh. Retrieved from <http://textilelearner.blogspot.com/2014/07/rmg-leading-earning-sector-in-bangladesh.html>
- Islam, M. S., and Ahmed, S. (2010, July 10). Contemplating Sustainable Solutions to Garments Sector Unrest. *The Daily Star*, p.8.

- Islam M. A., (2013). Sustainable business Environment, A Challenge for future, *24th Batexpo- 2013*. pp. 27-28.
- Islam, S. M., Faruk, O. M., Khatun, R. & Rahman, E. M. (2014). Conflict Between Workers And Organization In RMG Sector Where Security Of Sustainable Human Resource Development: A Study On Dhaka City, Bangladesh. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention, Volume- 3 Issue -4, PP.52-66*.
- Islam. R, & Maruf., K. N. (2014). Impact of EU GSP Facilities on Export Growth of Bangladesh: Especially On Readymade Garments Industry, *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, Volume 3, Issue 9, pp. 101-102
- Islam, M. A. (2015, April 13). Accord and Alliance conditions affecting RMG sector, *bdnews24.com*.
- Islam, M. A., (2015). RMG 2021- \$50 Billion on the 50th Anniversary of Bangladesh, *Dhaka Apparel Summit*. pp.41-44.
- Islam, M.A., (2015, March 08,). Prospects and challenges of garment industry, *The daily Star*, P.11.
- Khan, N.A. (2010). *Baseline survey for better work in textiles & garments (BWTG)*, p. 29
- Khan, S. (2011, January 30). Labour unrest and compliance issue in garment sector. *Financial Express*; 18(231).
- Khan, V.A., (2014, December 7). RMG Sector: Challenges & Way Forward, *Dhaka Tribune*, Retrieved from <http://www.dhakatribune.com/feature/2014/dec/07/rmg-sector-challenges-way-forward#sthash.f0VleseL.dpuf>
- Labowitz, S., & Pauly, D. B. (2014). *Business as Usual is not a Potion: Supply Chains and Sourcing after Rana Plaza*. Center for Business and Human Rights: NYU, STERN.
- Mahmud R.B. (2012). Skills development in Bangladesh RMG sector, *The News Today*, Retrieved from <http://www.newstoday.com.bd>.
- Mala, D.A., (2015, May 26), Rise in tax on RMG exporters' incomes likely in new budget. *The Financial Express*, P. 5.
- Mazedul, I. M., Maroof, K. A., & Monirul, I. M. (2013). Textile Industries in Bangladesh and Challenges of Growth. *Research Journal of Engineering Sciences*, Vol. 2(2), 31-37.
- Mezba, M. U. (2014). How Bangladeshi Ready Made Garments Industry can be competitive in the global Market. *Business Economics and Tourism*.
- Moazzem, H. (2012, July 4), FDI in RMG sector, *Financial Express*, Vol 20, no 231, Regd no da1589, Retrieved from http://www.thefinancialexpress-bd.com/old/more.php?news_id=135385&date=2012-07-04
- Mustafizur, R. M., (2015). 'The successful completion of ongoing remedial process is one of the key challenges to the country's export in the New Year,' *New Age*. Retrieved from <http://newagebd.net/82038/compliance-political-dev-key-challenges-to-rmg-sector-in-2015/#sthash.aFecwfr1.dpuf>.
- McKinsey & Company (2011). *Bangladesh's Ready-made Garments Landscape: The Challenge of Growth*. Frankfurt: McKinsey & Company, p.16.

- Mirdha, U. R., (2009, June 7). Lack of research sets back RMG. *The Daily Star*, <http://archive.thedailystar.net/newDesign/news-details.php?nid=91474>
- Nathan, D. (2013). 'Industrial relations in a GPN perspective: From tripartite to quadripartite machinery'. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 48(30): 29-33.
- Paul-Majumder, P. (1998). *Health Status of the Garment Workers in Bangladesh: Findings from a Survey of Employers and Employees*. Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies, Dhaka. 24 (1): 204-225.
- Quddus, M., and Rashid, S. (1999). Garment Exports from Bangladeshi: An Update and Evaluation. *Journal of Business Studies*, 1 (1):28-38.
- Rahman, M. (2002), "Bangladesh's External Sector in FY2001: Review of Performance and Emerging Concerns", in Sobhan, R. (ed) *Bangladesh Facing the Challenges of Globalisation: A Review of Bangladesh's Development*, Centre for Policy Dialogue, Dhaka.
- Rahman, N., and Anwar, G.M.J. (2007). Sustainability of RMG Sector of Bangladesh as a Globally Competitive Industry: Porters Diamond Perspective. *Journal of Business Studies*, 28(2): 99-132.
- Rahman, M., Bhattacharya, D. & Moazzem, K. G. (2008). *Bangladesh Apparel Sector in Post MFA Era: A Study on the Ongoing Restructuring Process*. Dhaka: Centre for Policy Dialogue in association with IFC and SEDF.
- Razib H., (2015). *Foreign Direct Investment on Bangladeshi Garments and textiles Sector: An overview of the foreign ownership in Bangladesh Garments and textiles (Bachelor Thesis, Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences)*
- Razzaue A., & Eusuf A., (2007, April). *Trade, Development and Poverty Linkage: Case Study of Ready Made Garment Industry in Bangladesh*, Unnayan Shamannay, Dhaka,
- Reddy, B., (2014, December 7). RMG Sector: Challenges & Way Forward, *Dhaka Tribune*, Retrieved from <http://www.dhakatribune.com/feature/2014/dec/07/rmg-sector-challenges-way-forward#sthash.f0VleseL.dpuf>.
- Rehman S. & Khundker N., ed. (2001): *Globalisation and Gender; Changing Patterns of Woman's Employment in Bangladesh*, Centre for Policy Dialogue, University Press Limited, Dhaka.
- Report casts shadow on RMG Sector: Challenges & Way Forward. (2014, December 7). *Dhaka Tribune*, P.07
- Report casts shadow on Denim and Jeans (2014), Retrieved from <http://denimsandjeans.com/bdshow/bangladesh.php>
- Robbani, M.G. (2000). World Trade Organisation and the Ready Made Garment Industry of Bangladesh: A Critical Analysis. *Journal of Business Studies*, 2(2): 16-27.
- Rock, M. (2001). Globalisation and Bangladesh: The Case of Export Oriented Garment Manufacture. *South Asia*, 24(1): 201- 225. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00856400108723430>
- Sarwar, S.K. (2013), Problems of the Bangladesh RMG sector, *The News Today*, http://www.newstoday.com.bd/index.php?option=details&news_id=2347128&date=2013-06-07

- Sattar, Z. (2015). Strategy for Export Diversification 2015-2020: Breaking into new markets with new: Policy Research Institute of Bangladesh
- Schwab, K. (2014). The Global Competitiveness Report on World economic Forum, Geneva.
- Shahriar, M. F., Banik, B.P., & Habib, M. M. (2014). A research framework of supply chain management in readymade garments industry of Bangladesh. *International Journal of Business and Economics Research*, 3(6-1): 38-44. doi: 10.11648/j.ijber.s.2014030601.16
- Siddiqi, H.G.A. (2005). *The Ready Made Garment Industry of Bangladesh*. (2nd ed.). Dhaka: The University Press Limited.
- Uddin, M.S., and Jahed, M.A. (2007). Garments Industry: A Prime Mover of the Social Economic Development of Bangladesh. *The Cost and Management*, 35(1): 59-70.
- Yunus, M. and Yamagata, T., (2012). The Garment Industry in Bangladesh, Fukunishi ed., *Dynamics of the Garment Industry in Low-Income Countries: Experience of Asia and Africa* (Interim Report). Chousakenkyu Houkokusho, IDE-JETRO.
- World Bank (1999). *Bangladesh: Key Challenges for the Next Millennium*. p. 27.
- World Bank, (2015). Retrieved from <http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FR.INR.LEND/countries/1W?display=default>
- Wayss, R., (2015, March- April). Transformation of RMG Industry. *The Apparel Story*, p. 10.
- Wayss, R., (2014, December 7). RMG Sector: Challenges & Way Forward, *Dhaka Tribune*, Retrieved from <http://www.dhakatribune.com/feature/2014/dec/07/rmg-sector-challenges-way-forward#sthash.f0VlseL.dpuf>
- Zadeed, R., (2013). Environmental Forces and SWOT Analysis of Garments. Retrieved from http://issuu.com/zadeed/docs/environmental_forces_and_swot_analysis_of_garments?e=8245881/3561752
- Ziaur R. (2012, June 1). Should RMG Welcome FDI? \$50bn Export Target, Retrieved from Business Outlook, http://businessoutlookbd.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=1080:should-rmg-welcome-fdi-&catid=43:magazine-news